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CONSTRUCTION AND QUALIFICATION WITH BEAM OF $10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$, 2 M LONG, PROTOTYPES

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Abstract:

This document describes (1) the assembly procedure developed to build a prototype dual-readout calorimeter designed for hadronic containment (had-size prototype), (2) the readout integration developed for the highly granular modules (equipped with SiPMs) and (3) the performance obtained with electron beams up to 120 GeV.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2025

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Executive summary

The main goal of this subtask is to develop the technology to build a hadronic-size dual-readout prototype made of 16 modules, $\sim 13 \times 13 \times 250$ cm³ each, targeting a standalone hadronic resolution in the range of 30 – 40 %/ \sqrt{E} for both single hadrons and jets with a constant term of $\sim 1\%$ or below. The R&D study aims to identify modular and scalable solutions for both the construction strategy and the readout scheme.

The assembly procedure and the mechanical precision achieved by using stainless steel tubes with an outer diameter of 2 mm, filled with 1 mm clear and scintillating fibres, were discussed in Milestone 35. Since then, 63 minimodules have been produced (5 minimodules form a module) and 36 have been already qualified with electron beams at the CERN SPS.

In this document, we report about:

- (1) the mechanical precision achieved during the production,*
- (2) the strategy identified to integrate the highly granular readout (based on SiPMs) that allows all services to be on the back of the absorber,*
- (3) the performance achieved by these minimodules when exposed to electron beams up to 120 GeV.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The dual-readout technique is a calorimetric approach designed to largely eliminate the energy measurement fluctuations due to a "non-compensated" response of the detector to the different hadronic shower components. It is based on the independent and simultaneous measurement of the scintillation and Cherenkov light produced in the detector by hadronic showers. The scintillation photons are correlated with the energy deposited by all ionising particles, while the Cherenkov photons are mainly correlated with the electromagnetic component of the shower. By the ratio of the two signals, it is possible to determine the electromagnetic fraction event-by-event and accurately estimate the energy of the primary particle [1].

The assembly procedure discussed in Milestone 35 is based on the results obtained with a smaller prototype (10×10 cm² large and 1m long) built in 2021 [2] and qualified on beam in 2021 and 2023 [3], modified to comply with the new design. Each minimodule consists of 2.5 m long capillary tubes arrays with an outer diameter of 2 mm and an inner diameter of 1.1 mm. The capillaries are manufactured by an external company and the high quality of the production allowed to simplify the tooling with respect to what was used for the 2021 prototype.

Each minimodule is assembled by gluing layers of capillary tubes positioned on a rectified reference plane. Each new layer is pre-aligned and then held with a vacuum system during the glue distribution phase before being moved to its final position above the other layers. This technique has proven to be fast and to guarantee excellent precision and good reproducibility. When all layers are stacked on top of each other, a calibrated weight is placed on top during the glue curing to improve the module flatness. Finally, once the minimodule is completed, the fibres are manually inserted in each tube, in alternating rows of scintillating and clear fibres.

The assembly technique has been qualified and the production of all the minimodules required to build the hadronic-size demonstrator is progressing well. The results of the production are discussed

in section 2, while the procedure identified to equip a fraction of the minimodules with SiPMs will be discussed in section 3. These are known as highly granular minimodules, to distinguish them from the standard ones read out with PMTs. Finally, in section 4 we report the results obtained with 36 standard minimodules qualified with electron beams of energies up to 120 GeV.

2. MINIMODULE PRODUCTION

2.1. MATERIAL QAQC

In order to guarantee that all the materials used in the minimodule assembly meet the required tolerances, a quality assurance and quality control procedure has been put in place.

In the case of capillary tubes, the straightness is checked by rolling the tube on a rectified table to identify kinks, while the edges are controlled to check that they are not crushed. The external diameter is measured on the granite table with the same tool used to measure the minimodule, as described in the Milestone 35 document. A sample of about 5% of each bundle is measured and Fig. 1 shows the distribution of the outer diameter. The request of $2 \text{ mm} \pm 0.030 \text{ mm}$ is fully met. The inner diameter was measured as a pass-fail test performed with a reference fibre and no issues were observed. In some cases, the capillary was obstructed, probably due to cleaning residuals. During the procedure, we added a step in which we blew air at high pressure in the capillary tubes. Finally, the length control is performed during the assembly phase by positioning the tubes on the reference plane. The overall rejection factor is approximately 3%.

Fig. 1 Distribution of capillary tube external diameters.

The two types of fibres are shipped in spools and cut at a length of 2.9 m, 40 cm longer than the tubes, to allow them to be bundled and to fit the PMT sensitive area (standard module) while the fibres used to equip the highly granular modules are cut to the same length as the capillaries. In this case, the SiPMs are in contact with the capillaries (Section 3).

A fraction of scintillating fibres was measured for both attenuation length and relative light response. A small fraction was found to have a reduced attenuation length and the problem was traced back to some microcracks in the fiber, probably due to fibre handling. Furthermore, in some cases, the scintillating fibres show protuberances in the outer diameter, which prevent the fibre from being inserted into the capillary tubes. The company (Luxium) is working to improve this aspect. Some measurements were also performed on the clear fibres but, as all the specifications were met, no sampling tests were performed during the production.

2.2. MODULE ASSEMBLY AND QAQC

The assembling procedure was described in the Milestone 35 document, here we report some numbers on the quality of the production. Fig. 2 (top) shows the trend of the maximum, minimum and average thickness of the minimodules produced so far as a function of the module number. After the initial fine-tuning phase, we achieved a stable condition. In fact, after further improving the assembly equipment with a reference plate placed on top of the minimodule during the glue curing, we reduced the RMS of the planarity measurements from $\sim 40 \mu\text{m}$ RMS to less than $15 \mu\text{m}$ RMS (Fig. 2 bottom).

Fig. 2 Thickness of the minimodule: average, minimum and maximum (top); RMS of the distribution of the 90 measured points on the module surface (bottom).

Once the module assembly is complete, the fibres are manually inserted into the capillary tubes. The two types of fibres are kept separated and inserted into a 3D printed holder as shown in Fig.3. The fibres are glued in a vertical position with an optical glue. Once cured, the fibres are polished and ready to be interfaced to PMTs via another plastic holder (see Fig. 3 right).

Fig. 3 Gluing procedure for the optical fibres (left); Two minimodules completed with fibres (right). The fibre's surface was polished and then the fibres inserted in the PMT holders

3. ASSEMBLY PROCEDURE OF HIGHLY GRANULAR MINIMODULES

The central part of the hadronic-size demonstrator is designed to be read out by SiPMs. The minimodule assembly strategy discussed in the previous sections also meets the more stringent requirements imposed by the highly granular minimodules. The main differences are: (1) avoid oversampling at the back of the calorimeter due to fibre grouping as required to match the sensitive area of the PMTs, (2) each SiPM must be aligned to its fibre to ensure uniformity response, (3) avoid contamination of the Cherenkov light by the, much more intense, scintillation light and, finally, (4) all mechanical supports and services, necessary for the operation of the SiPMs, must fit in the rear part of the absorber, to avoid inhomogeneities to propagate when the minimodules are stacked on top of each other.

A series of drawings, with details of the highly granular minimodule assembly, are shown in Fig. 4. To avoid oversampling, all fibres remain inside the capillaries while the sensitive area of each SiPM goes in contact with them. The SiPMs are assembled in bars by the company, interspaced by 2 mm to match the pitch of the capillaries in the row. Since all SiPMs must be in contact with the fibres, this face of the calorimeter is used as the reference plane and any irregularities (due to small errors in the length of the tubes) are absorbed at the front face, where precision requirements are more relaxed. Finally, to improve the light collection, optical grease is interposed between SiPMs and fibres.

Fig. 4. Details of the highly granular minimodule design. Highly granular minimodule with all services (i.e. SiPMs, pcb, mechanical supports and cables) (top left). Zoom showing the positioning of the micro-pcb assembly between the longer capillaries to feed the clear fibres, while the macro-pcb assembly is located at the back (top right). Below, from left to right, an exploded view of the micro-pcb assembly (SiPM bar with micro-pcb, mechanical support, cables and alignment pins), macro-pcb with 16 SiPM bars and the mechanical support (center) and the whole macro-pcb assembly.

Light contamination is avoided by alternating short and long tubes (Fig. 4, top right), the former fed with clear fibres and the latter with scintillating fibres. This mechanical structure is then used to guide the alignment of the SiPMs with respect to the clear fibres (short tubes). A bar of SiPMs is mounted on the micro-pcb where the current of the 8 sensors is summed in parallel to reduce the amount of services (only two coaxial cables per micro-pcb are used) and the number of channels to be read out. The shape of the micro-pcb follows the profile of the capillaries to ensure precise alignment between the SiPMs and the centre of the capillaries. Fig. 4 (bottom left) shows an exploded view of the micro-pcb assembly with all components clearly visible. The mechanical supports are 3D printed and the design has been optimised to have both rigidity and a large internal cavity to be filled with a two-component glue (Araldite 2011). The glue provides strength to the assembly and insulates the electrical contacts of the coaxial cables. This mechanical support also serves to house two pins used as an alignment reference for the macro-pcb assembly.

The macro-pcb is equipped with 16 SiPM bars and, also in this case, the current of the 8 SiPMs in each bar is summed in parallel. The mechanical support structure is glued to the back of the macro-pcb to give rigidity to the board and to avoid mechanical stress to the soldered cables. A series of openings is used as a feed-through for the coaxial cables serving the micro-pcb and alignment holes (0.9 mm in diameter) are inserted into the macro-pcb to: (1), ensure proper positioning of the SiPMs of the macro-pcb with respect to the fibres and, (2), gently push the micro-pcb assembly into its final position. The macro-pcb assembly is held in place with four metal wires (with a 100 μm diameter) running along the absorbing material between adjacent capillaries and clamped on the front face of the calorimeter. The wire tension is calibrated with a dynamometer to avoid unwanted stresses on the components. The drawings at the top of Fig. 4 show the result of the final assembly.

Fig. 5. A series of pictures of the first integration test performed with dummies components. Positioning of the macro-pcb assembly (left), clearance test to check the compatibility of the positioning of adjacent macro-pcb assemblies (centre), final fixing with metal wires (right).

To qualify the assembly procedure, dummy components were produced. At this stage, the SiPM bars and the pcb (micro and macro) were also 3D printed. The mechanical tools required to build the assembled system were produced and qualified with these components. The mechanical tools serve to align and hold the wires during soldering¹ and keep the mechanical support in contact with the pcb during glue curing. The compliance of the micro-pcb assembly with the specifications was verified by placing the assembly between the longest tubes of the minimodule during the integration test.

The first stage of the integration test consists of inserting the 16 micro-pcbs assemblies between the longer capillary rows. The cables are then inserted into the opening of the macro-pcb, which is then moved into position. This is the most delicate part because all the alignment pins must fit into the holes of the macro-pcb. The test was successful and the pictures in Fig. 5 show the salient steps: the alignment between the macro-pcb and the alignment pins (left), the positioning of two adjacent macro-pcbs (centre) and a zoom on the wire that keeps the macro-pcb attached to the absorber (right). To demonstrate that all services are kept in the envelope of the absorber, the minimodule was moved on top of one of the standard minimodules already filled with the fibres and ready for the tests. Fig. 6 shows the quality of the assembly and the zoomed image on the right demonstrates that, with this strategy, we don't need mechanical structures outside the envelope.

¹ Soldering was clearly not possible with dummy components, the wires were simply held in place during the curing of the glue. The soldering procedure was tested with real components. In this case, also the functionality of the SiPMs and the quality of the multiphoton spectra were verified. These assemblies were not used for the integration test.

Fig. 6. The pictures show the mechanical compatibility of the highly granular dummy minimodule with the standard ones (served by PMTs) when placed in position. In the enlarged image on the right, one can better appreciate the absence of external mechanical structures that could have created dead areas.

4. TEST BEAM RESULTS

A dual-readout prototype, consisting of 36 standard minimodules arranged in 12 rows and 3 columns ($38.4 \times 33.7 \times 250 \text{ cm}^3$), was constructed using the technique described in Section 2 and tested with particles at the SPS at CERN in 2024. Each minimodule was equipped with two Hamamatsu R8900 PMTs, one connected to the Cherenkov fibres and the other to the scintillating ones. The prototype was positioned, with respect to the beam line (z-axis), at a small angle of 2.5° in both the x and y directions, to mitigate the channeling effect observed in previous beam tests [3]. A series of auxiliary detectors were placed along the beam line (Fig. 7) to identify and select different particles. Moving in the direction of the beam, upstream of the prototype, were installed:

- Three Cherenkov counters, with H_2 pressure optimised to distinguish between electrons and pions or muons, for beam energies up to approximately 40 GeV.
- Three thin plastic scintillators, used to generate the trigger signal.
- A pair of delay wire chambers, employed to select particles hitting the centre of the prototype front face.
- A preshower detector (1 X_0 of lead, before a scintillator plate), to improve the electron identification performance.

Downstream, only a plastic scintillator was installed to identify muons.

This setup ensured precise particle selection and beam characterisation, supporting the accurate evaluation of the dual-readout prototype performance. Since the prototype was still too small to largely contain showers from hadrons, the results shown in this paragraph refer only to positron beams.

Fig. 7. The pictures show the 36 minimodules ready to be installed in the test beam area (left), the test beam setup (top right) and the test beam schema with the calorimeter and all ancillaries detectors (bottom right).

The signals of the ancillary detectors were used to define a positron selection procedure capable of excluding muons and pions as well as pathological events, with a selection efficiency ranging from 40% to 55%, depending on the beam energy. By examining the scintillation energy distribution after the selection, a ‘double peak’ structure was observed. This was later correlated to the impact point, along the Y axis, of the particle on the front face of the calorimeter. In particular, an impact point on the lower half of the calorimeter face corresponded to a lower reconstructed scintillation energy. Although the cause of this behaviour is not yet fully understood, it is evident that it exhibits the same characteristics at all energies, as shown in Fig. 8 (left), where the normalised profiles of the scintillation and Cherenkov energies are shown. Thanks to this observation, it was possible to develop a global correction factor for all energies and for both scintillation and Cherenkov signals. After applying the correction and performing a calibration procedure to match the measured energy to the nominal beam energy, an electromagnetic energy resolution estimation was carried out. The data were fitted considering a sampling term ($\sim 1/\sqrt{E}$), a noise term ($\sim 1/E$), and a constant term. The results, shown in Fig. 8 (right), are presented separately for the Cherenkov signal (blue), scintillation signal (grey), and their weighted average (red), achieving a sampling term of approximately 15%.

Fig. 8. The plots on the left show the normalised energy profile of the scintillating (top) and Cherenkov (bottom) signals as a function of the impact point of the tracks along the y axis. Each colour refers to a different beam energies. The right plot shows the energy resolution obtained after the correction [4]. See text for further details.

In order to assess the performance with hadrons, a dual-readout prototype large enough to contain hadron-originated showers is under construction made of 80 minimodules, with a total cross section of $65 \times 65 \text{ cm}^2$ and a length of 2.5 m (about 10.5 interaction lengths). The deposited energy for hadron showers inside the calorimeter volumes, estimated through Geant4 simulations in the [10–100] GeV energy range, is around 93%. The central part of the prototype (10 out of the 80 minimodules) will be read out with SiPMs, choice driven by the need of a compromise between cost (and complexity) and performance. The qualification of this prototype is out of the scope of this document but we expect to test it on beam in 2025 and 2026 at the CERN’s SPS. Nevertheless, for completeness, we include the expected energy resolution in response to pions. The plot in Fig. 9 is obtained with a Geant4 simulation based on the geometry of the discussed demonstrator together with the results from the previous test beam [3,4,5]. The energy resolution refers to single pions, generated at different energies and reconstructed with the dual-readout method. A linear sum of the stochastic and constant components of the relative energy resolution was used in the fit, as a better agreement was found with respect to a quadratic sum. The results are compatible with the desired performance if one takes into account the lateral energy leakage due to the detector size.

Fig. 9. Geant4 simulation-based energy resolution for hadron showers originated by positively charged pions impinging on the HiDRa dual-readout prototype [5].

5. CONCLUSIONS

The construction of a hadronic-size calorimeter prototype is ongoing and 63 over 80 minimodules have been produced to date. Preliminary tests of a prototype made of 12×3 minimodules were carried out in 2024 at the CERN SPS. The data taken are still under analysis but looks compatible with expectations. They will allow us to better define and tune the calibration procedure, opening the way for the final tests of the full prototype in 2025 and 2026.

6. REFERENCES

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